

Research Article

Development of Controlled Release Microspheres of amoxicillin by using Natural Gums

Afreen Khan^{*1}, Arpita Verma², Ashutosh Rajak³, Dhawal Pal⁴, Rajat Pawar⁵

^{1,2}NMT Gujarati College of Pharmacy, Indore M.P

³Ujjain Institute of Pharmaceutical Sciences

⁴The Indore Management Institute (IMI) Pharmaceutical Studies

⁵Swami Vivekanand College of Pharmacy, Indore

ARTICLE INFO

Published: 18 Mar. 2025

Keywords:

Amoxicillin, microspheres,
guar gum, xanthan gum

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15041886

ABSTRACT

The present investigation aimed to formulate and evaluate in vitro performances of controlled release amoxicillin microspheres for the potential application in the treatment of gastric and duodenal ulcers, which were associated with *Helicobacter pylori*. Method: Amoxicillin control release microspheres containing as guar gum and xanthan gum as control release polymer were prepared by an external ionotropic gelation method using sodium alginate and calcium chloride. The prepared microspheres were evaluated for their micromeritic properties, drug content and encapsulation efficiency and characterized by Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy, differential scanning calorimetry, X-ray diffraction and scanning electron microscopy. The *in vitro* release studies were performed by buffer change method using pH 1.2 buffer and pH 6.8 phosphate buffer. Results: The preliminary trials results indicate that quantity of gelling agent, drug-to-polymers ratio, time for stirring and speed of rotation has impact on the characteristics of microspheres. The prepared microspheres were half white, free flowing, spherical in shape with mean particle size in the range of 450 to 779 μm . The drug-loaded microspheres showed 60.42-89.23% of entrapment and *in vitro* drug release was extended up to 12 hr releasing 18.9 –93.86 % of the total drug from the microspheres. The optimized formulation batch exhibited high drug entrapment efficiency of 83%, the particle size was 450 μm and a controlled drug release was observed for more than 12 hr. The infrared spectra showed stable character of amoxicillin in the drug-loaded microspheres and revealed the absence of drug-polymer interactions. The morphological characteristics of the microspheres were studied under a scanning electron microscopy revealed that the microspheres were spherical and porous in nature. *In vitro* release studies showed that amoxicillin released bit slightly faster in pH 1.2 gastric fluid than in pH 7.8 phosphate buffer. The release kinetics was achieved with Koresmeyer-Peppas plot followed by zero order with Fickian diffusion mechanism.

***Corresponding Author:** Afreen Khan

Address: NMT Gujarati College of Pharmacy, Indore M.P

Email ✉: rajatpawar74@gmail.com

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

Conclusions: The prolonged gastrointestinal residence time and enhanced amoxicillin stability resulting from the amoxicillin microspheres might make a contribution to *H. pylori* complete eradication

INTRODUCTION

The oral route is considered to be most convenient for the administration of drugs to patients. The oral administration of different dosage forms is the most common form of administration due to greater patient compliance and flexibility. Where drug normally dissolves in the gastro-intestinal fluids and is absorbed from these regions of the gastro-intestinal tract, and both process depends upon the physicochemical properties of the drug [1-4]. The dosage form is modified to deliver the drug at the target region or at the disease region is known as targeted drug delivery system [5]. Drugs which show poor absorption from the stomach as intestine including peptide are most suitable for controlled drug delivery system. Novel drug delivery aim is to deliver the drug at a rate directed by the needs of the body during the period of treatment and channel the active entity to the site of action. A number of novel drug delivery systems have emerged encompassing various routes of administration to achieve controlled and targeted drug delivery. Microspheres based drug delivery systems has received considerable attention in recent years. Hence, microspheres of degradable and non-biodegradable polymers have been investigated for sustained or controlled release based on their application [6]. Generally, antibiotics acts against bacterial activity by inhibiting the synthesis of bacterial cell walls. Amoxicillin is a semi-synthetic penicillin and is a simply the hydroxyl analogue of ampicillin. It acts against bacterial activity by inhibiting the synthesis of bacterial cell wall and also specifically stops the cross-linkage between the linear peptidoglycan polymer chains that make up a major component of the bacterial cell wall. It is used in the treatment of bacillary dysentery, stomach ulcers, intestinal ulcers caused by the bacteria *H. Pylori* and to prevent the ulcers from

returning. Amoxicillin is rapidly absorbed after oral administration. Mostly amoxicillin is excreted unchanged in the urine. It binds to blood serum and is approximately 20% protein binding and its plasma elimination half-life is 1 hour, in order to maintain therapeutic plasma levels, the drug must be administered approximately 750-1000 mg daily by oral individual dosage [7-17]. Amoxicillin belongs to BCS class III, its solubility has to be improved. Hence the present research work was aimed to develop amoxicillin microspheres by external ionotropic gelation method.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials: Amoxicillin, guar gum and xanthan gum were purchased from Yarrow Chem products, Mumbai, India. Sodium alginate was purchased from Finar Chemicals, Mumbai, India. Calcium chloride anhydrous was purchased from HiMedia Labs, Pvt. Ltd. Mumbai, India. Hydrochloride and potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate were purchased from Yarrow chem.Products, Mumbai, India. All other chemicals and reagents used in this study were of analytical grade.

METHODS:

Pre-formulation studies: Before design of the dosage forms of a amoxicillin pre-formulation studies such as organoleptic characterization, melting point, UV-Visible spectrophotometer, and fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy studies were performed to know the quality and purity of the drug. Drug content estimation, compatibility studies like visual inspection, FTIR spectroscopy, Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) studies.

Compatibility studies: These studies were performed to know the compatibility of drug and excipients by using FTIR, DSC, XRD and SEM.

Method of preparation: The microspheres were prepared by external ionotropic gelation method. Sodium alginate in combination with various polymers such as guar gum and xanthan gum in

different ratios were taken. Sodium alginate was dissolved in distilled water to form homogeneous polymer solutions with each polymer. The drug amoxicillin (100 mg) was added to the polymer solution and the resulting dispersion was added manually drop wise into 5 % w/v of calcium chloride solution with stirring at 1000 rpm to complete the curing reaction to form

microspheres. The microsphere was collected and dried in hot air oven. The microspheres were washed several times and dried at room temperature for 3 hr. The microspheres were stored in a desiccator containing calcium chloride. The composition of microspheres formulations was given in **Table No. 1**

Table No. 1: Formulation of amoxicillin microspheres.

Formulation Code (mg)	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8	F9	F10	F11	F12	F13	F14	F15
Drug	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Sodium	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200	200
Guar gum	50	75	100	125	150	200	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	50	75
Xanthan gum	-	-	-	-	-	-	50	75	100	125	150	200	250	-	-

All the formulation contains 5% w/v calcium chloride.

Evaluation of amoxicillin microspheres

Organoleptic properties: Organoleptic properties such as appearance, odour and colour were identified.

Micromeritic properties: Micrometric properties like angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, Carr’s index and Hausner’s ratio of the prepared microspheres were studied [8, 9].

Angle of repose: The flow characteristics of microspheres were assessed by determining the angle of repose. Determination of angle of repose of amoxicillin microspheres were carried out by employing fixed funnel method by using Eq. 1.

(1)

$$\text{Angle of repose } (\theta) = \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{h}{r} \right]$$

Bulk density and tapped density: Initial volume (Vo) was measured and then, the density apparatus was set for 100 taps and after that, the volume (Vf)

$$\text{Percentage yield } (\%) = \frac{\text{Weight of the microspheres}}{\text{Total weight of drug + polymer taken}} \times 100$$

Drug content estimation: Accurately weighed quantity (equivalent to 100 mg of drug) of microspheres was crushed into powder and added

was measured. The bulk density and tapped density were calculated by using formulas given in Eq. 2 and Eq. 3 where W- is weight of prepared microspheres.

(2)

$$\text{Bulk density} = \frac{W}{V_o}$$

(3)

$$\text{Tapped density} = \frac{W}{V_f}$$

Hausner’s ratio: It measures the ratio of the final volume to initial volume and can be calculated by using Eq. 4.

(4)

$$\text{Hausner's ratio} = \frac{V_o}{V_f}$$

Carr’s index: To analyze the flow ability, the Carr’s index is calculated on the basis of the bulk density and tapped density. It can be calculated by using Eq. 5.

$$\text{Carr's index } (\%) = \left[\frac{V_o}{V_f} \right] \times 100$$

Percentage yield: The percentage yield was calculated by using Eq. 6.

to 100 ml of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer. The resulting mixture was kept stirring for 2 hours and kept it a side over night. The solution was diluted using pH 6.8 phosphate buffer and analyzed

spectrophotometrically at 230 nm to get practical drug content [10].

Drug entrapment or encapsulation efficiency:

The drug entrapment efficiency was calculated by Eq. 7.

$$\text{Drug entrapment efficacy (\%)} = \frac{\text{Practical drug content}}{\text{Theoretical drug content}} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

Particle size analysis: The particle size can be identified with the help of optical microscope in the range of 0.2 to 500 μm . The particle size was measured using an optical microscope and the mean microsphere diameter was calculated by measuring 50 particles with the help of a calibrated ocular micrometer.

Swelling studies: A known weight ≈ 50 mg of microspheres was placed in a glass vial containing 10 ml of distilled water at 37 ± 0.5 °C in incubator with occasional shaking. The microspheres were periodically removed, bottled with filter paper and their changes in weights were measured during the swelling until equilibrium was attained. Finally, the weight of the swollen microspheres was recorded after a period of 3 hours and the swelling ration (SR) was then calculated from the formula given in Eq. 8. The studies were carried out in triplicate.

(8)

$$\text{Swelling Index (SI)} = \frac{W_t - W_o}{W_o} \times 100$$

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) studies:

The FTIR spectra of the amoxicillin, Optimized formulation, guar gum, xanthan gum using KBr pellet technique, samples were scanned over the range of 400-4000 cm^{-1} at the spectral resolution of 4 cm^{-1} [11].

Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC): The DSC analysis of indomethacin and optimized formulation were carried out to evaluate any

possible drug polymer interaction. The DSC analysis was performed in the range of 20 °C to 300 °C temperature at a rate of 10 °C/min with 25 ml/min of nitrogen flow [12].

X-ray Powder Diffractometry (XRD): The XRD studies of indomethacin and optimized formulation were recorded using Philips X-ray diffractometry (Ultima-III, Rigaku, Japan) with copper target to investigate the effect of microencapsulation on crystallinity of drug [13].

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) studies:

The SEM analysis of indomethacin and optimized formulation microspheres powder were taken using a scanning electron microscope (JSM 6360, Joel make, UK). Samples were fixed on an aluminum stub with conductive double-side adhesive tape.

In vitro drug release studies: Dissolution studies were carried out for 12 hours using basket type dissolution apparatus (USP-XXIII Electro lab, containing 900 mL of dissolution medium maintained at 37 ± 0.5 °C at 100 rpm speed. The dissolution was carried out first 2 hours in 1.2 pH buffer and followed by pH 6.8 phosphate buffers for next 10 hours with the respective sampling intervals 5 ml of aliquots were withdrawn and replaced with an equal volume of fresh prewarmed dissolution medium. After suitable dilutions, the samples were analyzed spectrophotometrically at 230 nm.

Release kinetics studies: Quantitative analysis of the values obtained in dissolution studies was used in mathematical formulae to express the dissolution results as function of dosage form characteristics.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Organoleptic properties: The organoleptic properties of amoxicillin were identified the appearance is as fine powder, odour is penicillin-type and white in color.

Micromeritic properties: The micromeritic properties of microspheres of all the batches F1-F15 were shown in **Table No. 2**. The angle of repose of prepared microspheres was found to be in the range of 9.64 to 16.47°. The bulk density of prepared microspheres was found to be between 0.32 to 0.50 gm/cm³, tapped density was 0.42 to 0.59 gm/cm³, Hausner's ratio 1.03 to 1.18 and Carr's index was found to be between 5.21 to 10.35 %. The flow properties of different batches of microcapsules were excellent as the angle of repose values were found to be less than 25°, compressibility index less than 12 % and Hausner's ratio less than 1.18 in all the batches.

Table No. 2: Micromeritic properties of amoxicillin microspheres.

S. No.	Formulation code	Angle of repose (θ°)	Bulk density (g/cm ³)	Tapped density (g/cm ³)	Hausner's ratio	Carr's index%
1.	F1	10.75±0.25	0.32±0.13	0.57±0.22	1.11	9.98
2.	F2	9.64±0.01	0.45±0.03	0.48±0.09	1.15	10.35
3.	F3	11.14±0.22	0.49±0.04	0.53±0.02	1.10	9.83
4.	F4	14.09±0.15	0.48±0.05	0.52±0.03	1.08	7.60
5.	F5	11.06±0.08	0.46±0.08	0.49±0.09	1.06	7.62
6.	F6	12.84±0.06	0.49±0.09	0.52±0.08	1.09	9.02
7.	F7	16.17±0.12	0.47±0.07	0.51±0.05	1.10	9.79
8.	F8	12.13±0.05	0.42±0.13	0.50±0.01	1.12	9.13
9.	F9	14.28±0.01	0.45±0.02	0.52±0.03	1.11	10.31
10.	F10	16.18±0.09	0.47±0.12	0.55±0.01	1.18	9.4
11.	F11	12.44±0.03	0.49±0.15	0.52±0.92	1.09	8.7
12.	F12	15.65±0.05	0.42±0.05	0.46±0.05	1.05	5.21
13.	F13	16.47±0.12	0.50±0.14	0.59±0.01	1.03	7.05
14.	F14	11.89±0.23	0.46±0.03	0.43±0.01	1.04	9.57
15.	F15	13.62±0.78	0.49±0.04	0.42±0.05	1.07	8.47

Where all the values are expressed as mean ± S.D., n=3.

Percentage yield, drug entrapment efficacy and drug content estimation: The percentage yield, drug entrapment efficacy and drug content of all prepared microspheres of different batches F1-F15 were given in the **Table No. 3**. Percentage yield

and entrapment efficiency of different batches were found to be in the range of 62.46 to 94.27 % and 60.428 % to 89.23 % respectively. The drug content of microspheres of different batches F1 – F10 were found to be in the range of 64.18 to 91.42 % respectively.

Table No. 3: Percentage yield, drug entrapment efficiency and drug content of amoxicillin microspheres.

S. No.	Formulation code	Theoretical yield (g)	Practical yield (g) ^a	Percentage yield (%) ^a	Entrapment efficiency ^a	Drug content ^a
1.	F1	2.43	2.1±0.13	86.41±0.21	79.26±0.18	73.51±0.52
2.	F2	1.25	1.1±0.04	88.07±0.12	73.64±0.16	76.89±0.84
3.	F3	1.68	1.15±0.12	68.24±0.13	75.58±0.13	79.64±0.45
4.	F4	2.65	2.37±0.09	86.66±0.16	83.68±0.08	84.18±0.16
5.	F5	2.25	1.94±0.11	85.08±0.11	82.23±0.11	65.42±0.75
6.	F6	2.18	1.56±0.14	71.88±0.09	60.42±0.12	76.92±0.91
7.	F7	2.85	2.15±0.10	87.65±0.10	72.31±0.09	88.45±0.41
8.	F8	3.84	2.86±0.08	74.09±0.12	61.32±0.13	64.18±0.28
9.	F9	2.22	1.95±0.16	88.28±0.14	82.31±0.07	83.64±0.34
10.	F10	3.39	2.23±0.07	65.59±0.13	83.57±0.21	85.42±0.19
11.	F11	3.72	2.25±0.09	62.46±0.11	84.46±0.12	86.92±0.32
12.	F12	2.35	2.19±0.16	93.19±0.06	88.20±0.05	75.42±0.44
13.	F13	2.28	2.15±0.08	94.27±0.12	89.23±0.09	89.64±0.45

14.	F14	3.56	3.35±0.11	86.59±0.08	81.57±0.14	74.18±0.55
15.	F15	2.35	1.89±0.05	82.17±0.17	86.41±0.18	91.42±0.75

Where all the values are expressed as mean ± S.D., n=3.

Particle size (μm): The average particle size range is $450\pm 1.25 \mu\text{m}$ to $779.5\pm 1.25 \mu\text{m}$. The major fraction of the microspheres (50-55%) of all batches were within a range from $450\mu\text{m}$ mesh size. The data was represented in **Table 4**.

Swelling Index (SI): swelling property of microspheres was prepared by using different concentration of natural gums like guar gum, xanthan gum. The swelling index range of all the prepared microspheres were in the range from 87% to 222%, values were given in **Table 4**.

Table No. 4: Particle size and swelling index of amoxicillin microspheres.

S. No.	Formulation code	Particle size (μm)	Swelling Index (%)
1.	F1	450±1.25	98±0.11
2.	F2	472±1.30	102±0.8
3.	F3	493±0.96	132±0.15
4.	F4	540±2.65	90±0.14
5.	F5	554±1.54	170±0.23
6.	F6	581±1.17	168±0.7
7.	F7	602±0.97	222±0.04
8.	F8	624±0.35	193±0.11
9.	F9	665±1.77	87±0.06
10.	F10	692±0.22	157±0.11
11.	F11	713±2.67	121±0.17
12.	F12	719±0.57	97±0.13
13.	F13	779±1.80	201±0.11
14.	F14	588±1.27	95±0.08
15.	F15	692±0.65	150±0.12

Where all the values are expressed as mean ± S.D., n=3.

Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (FTIR) studies: FTIR analysis describes about the drug:polymer interaction. **Figure 1**, shows IR spectrum of amoxicillin, xanthan gum and optimized formulation F13. The FTIR spectrum of amoxicillin showed the characteristic peaks at 3440 cm^{-1} (N-H Stretching), 1576 cm^{-1} (aromatic C=C Stretching), 2968 cm^{-1} (C-H Stretching), 1772.3 cm^{-1} (C=O Stretching), 1177.8 cm^{-1} CH₃ directly attached to the ring, 1246.6 cm^{-1} C-O-C in COOH. The similar drug result were reported by Kultida S et al. therefore, it was identified as amoxicillin in **Figure 1a**. The FTIR spectrum of

xanthan gum showed the absorption band nearly at 3268 cm^{-1} (O-H), 1718.3 cm^{-1} (C=O) and 2911.1 cm^{-1} (C-OH) stretching vibration. The same peaks were also reported in drug loaded microcapsules in optimized formulation F13, prepared using sodium alginate and its combination with xanthan gum. There was no change or shifting of characteristics peaks of amoxicillin in drug loaded microcapsules, suggested that there was no significant drug polymer interaction which indicated the stable nature of drug inside the formulation. This conformed the stability of the formulation.

Figure 3: XRD of a) Amoxicillin and b) Optimized formulation F13.

Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) studies: The microphotography of the microsphere was shown **Figure 4**. It suggests the prepared microspheres were free flowing nature. It was distinct, multinucleate and monolithic with even

geometry. Microphotograph also revealed that microspheres were round and totally wrapped with gums. Roughness of the microsphere surface indicated the presence of the drug.

Figure 4: SEM of a) Amoxicillin and b) Optimized formulation F13.

In vitro drug release studies: The % cumulative *in vitro* release studies were performed in triplicate (n=3) for all the prepared formulation F1 to F15 with different concentration of polymer in each formulation in 1.2 pH buffer for 12 hrs the samples were spectrophotometrically analyzed at 230 nm. Guar gum used microspheres containing amoxicillin release profile shown in **Figure 5a**. The formulations of guar gum showed in complete drug release within 12 hrs of dissolution. As the concentration of guar gum was increased the drug release pattern was decreased (F2). The formulation F3, F4, F5 showed similar drug release profile was F2 formulation. The formulation F1 to F6 contains similar quantities of sodium alginate 2 g. the amoxicillin release was less due to the more concentration of sodium

alginate. The sodium alginate forms high viscosity solutions where the amoxicillin was entrapped. Therefore, the amoxicillin release was less. The sodium alginate guar gum (2g) good matrix solution where the amoxicillin entrapped and showed higher release. The F14 to F15 formulation showed incomplete drug release. The formulation F7 to F13 was prepared by using various concentration of Xanthan gum with varying concentration of sodium alginate. The formulation F7 to F13 contains 2 g of sodium alginate with increasing concentration of xanthan gum. The F12 formulation showed approximately 93% of drug release within 12 hrs of dissolution were shown in **Figure 5b**. The F13 formulation showed a complete drug release and good release pattern within 3hrs dissolution showed

approximately 45% of drug release whereas at 6 hrs of dissolution it showed 70% of drug release. The formulation F14 to F15 in complete drug release (approximately 91 %). Among all the formulation of xanthan gum used amoxicillin microspheres, F13 formulation (0.250 g of xanthan gum, 1g of sodium alginate). Showed better

release profile over a period of 12 hrs. this may be due to increased concentration of xanthan gum and decrease concentration of sodium alginate. The combination of sodium alginate, xanthan gum maintained as appropriate gel barrier and tortosity. Therefore, F13 formulation was selected as optimized formulation.

Figure 4.14: In vitro drug release profile of a) Guar gum formulation F1 – F6, F14, F15 and b) Xanthan gum formulation F7 – F13.

Drug release kinetic study:

- Several kinetic models like zero order, first order, Higuchi model, Korsmeyer - Peppas model, Hixon Crowell was applied to the dissolution profiles of amoxicillin microspheres F13 and F14 and compared in order to find out the most probable kinetics of drug release. Various parameters like correlation coefficient, release rate constant and diffusion coefficient values estimated after linearization of dissolution data.
- Comparing the correlation coefficient values of zero order (0.8942), (0.9342) and first order (0.8815), (0.9022) it was found that drug release follows zero order kinetics indicating that drug release was independent concentration.
- In order to find out the release component (n) value, the release data was analyzed as per Korsmeyer-Peppas model. The 'n' value of F13, F14 batch was found to be 0.325, 0.331 ensuring that the drug release followed Fickian diffusion mechanism. This type of release behaviours was generally exhibited the swelling rate of the polymer and drug release.

The microspheres were evaluated for pre-compression parameters like angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density and Carr's index. The result obtained were found to be satisfactory and within specified limits. The drug entrapment efficiency and percentage yield increased progressively with increasing the concentration of polymer. The *in vitro* amoxicillin release studies were performed 0.1 N HCl buffer. In this investigation it was observed that out of all formulation (F1 to F15), the F13 (0.1 g drug, 0.250 g xanthan gum, 1g sodium alginate) shown a promising and effective controlled release of drug over a period of 12 hrs. The XRD and SEM supported the study. Hence F13 was considered as best formulation. Analysis of release data as per different kinetic models indicated that amoxicillin release from these microspheres was best fit towards zero order kinetics. Correlation coefficient values in the zero order models were higher than those first order, indicating the drug release was independent of drug concentration. Correlation coefficient (R²) values in Higuchi model suggest that the release of drug was following diffusion type of mechanism. When the release data of optimized batch F13 was analyzed as per Korsmeyer – Peppas equation, as the

CONCLUSION

release exponent 'n' indicating the Fickian diffusion mechanism. From the results we can conclude that design of microspheres by employing natural polymers as release retardants by external ionotropic gelation technique was widely used to encapsulate a broad range of drugs to achieve controlled delivery of drug. Natural polymer (xanthan gum) was a suitable release retardant polymer. It is showed its best along with another natural polymer, sodium alginate. The combination of sodium alginate and xanthan gum was suitable to develop microsphere, which showed better amoxicillin release over a period of 12 hrs. the external inotropic gelation method was a suitable method for the preparation of microsphere. The controlled amoxicillin microspheres were capable of maintaining constant plasma concentration up to 12 hrs. so this can expected to decrease the drug intake eventually and increasing the patient compliance which was the major drawback of conventional amoxicillin formulations. This combination of sodium alginate and xanthan gum can be used develop microspheres for other drugs.

REFERENCES

1. Bhushan PK, Kalyani VT, Vinayak SM, Sandeep SL. Colon targeted drug delivery system – A novel prespective. *Asain International journal of Biomedical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2(14); 2012: 21-28.
2. Goh CH, Heng PWS, Chan LW. Aliginates a useful natural polymers for microencapsulation and therapeutic applications. *Carbohydrates polymers*. 88; 2012: 1-12.
3. Dash S, Murthy PN, Nath LK, Chowdhury P. Kinetic modeling on drug release from controlled drug delivery systems. *Acta Poloniae Pharmaceutica-Drug Res*. 67(3); 2010: 217-223.
4. Altamash MQ, Munira M, Sudha R, Asish D, Chaitrali K. Colon targeted drug delivery system: A review on current approaches. *Indian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Biological Research*. 2013; 1(4); 130-147.
5. Amrita C, Hariom S. A Review: Different Approaches of Colon Targeted Drug Delivery System. *American Journal of Pharm Tech Research*. 2014; 4(6); 105-115. Yang YY, Chung TS, Bai XL, Chan WK. Effect of preparation condition protein fabricatd by double-emulsion method. *Chemical Engineering Science*. 2001; 55(12): 2223-2236.
6. Malleswari K, Vijaya R. Colon targeted drug delivery review and novel approaches. *WorldJournal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2016; 5(5); 1636-1650.
7. Chakraborty S, Dey BK, Saha S, Kar A, Saha B. Design and evaluation of floating microspheres of amoxicillin trihydrate by ionotropic gelation method. *Journal of Applied Pharmaceutical Research*. 2014; 2(1): 39-47.
8. Sweetman SC, Martindale. *The complete drug reference*. 33rd Edn. Pharmaceutical press: Great Britani; 2002: 41-42.
9. Subrahmanyam CVS. *Text book of Physical Pharmaceutics*. 2nd ed. New Delhi: Vallabh Prakashan. 2005; 210 - 228.
10. Lachman L, Lieberman A, Kinig JL. *The Theory and practice of Industrial Pharmacy*. 2nd ed. Varghese Publishing House. 1999; 67-74.
11. Paradkar M, Amin J. Formulation development and evaluation of colon targeted delayed release methotrexate pellets for the treatment of colonic carcinoma. *Brazilian Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*. 2018; 54(4): e17222.
12. Priese F, Frisch T, Wolf B. Comparison of film-coated retarded release pellets manufactured by layering technique or by bed rotor pelletization. *Pharm Develop Technol*. 2015; 20(4): 417-25.
13. Bohns FR, Leitune VCB, Garcia IM, Genari B, Dornelles NBJ, Guterres SS, Ogliari FA, Melo MAS, Collares FM. Incorporation of amoxicillin-loaded microspheres in mineral

- trioxide aggregate cement: an in vitro study. *Restorative Dentistry & Endodontics*. 2020; 45(4): e50.
14. Jignyasha AR, Jayvadan KP, Madhabhai MP. Formulation and in vitro characterization of spray dried microspheres of amoxicillin. *Acta Pharm.* 60 (2010) 455–465.
 15. Vishal G, Gowda DV, Balamuralidhara V, Khan MS. Preparation and comparative bioavailability studies of indomethacin loaded cetyl alcohol microspheres. *Journal of pharmaceuticals*. 2013;1(1): 1-9.
 16. Manjunatha M, Jadadish RL, Gowda DV, Mohammed SK. Preparation, evaluation and bioavailability studies of indomethacin loaded PEA polymeric microspheres for controlled drug delivery. *International journal of drug discovery* 2010: 1(2); 141 - 155.
 17. Senthil K, Avik KS, Kunchu K, Sanat KB. Preparation and characterization of indomethacin loaded ionically crosslinked microspheres using chitosan. *Scholars research library*. 2012, 4(1): 33-41

HOW TO CITE: Afreen Khan*, Arpita Verma, Ashutosh Rajak, Dhawal Pal, Rajat Pawar, Development of Controlled Release Microspheres of amoxicillin by using Natural Gums, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 3, 1577-1587. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15041886>